

THE ROLE OF USING AUTHENTIC VIDEO MATERIALS IN EFL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract. This investigation is tending to the usage of video materials as a fundamental technique during the time spent materials plan inside the region of EFL/ESL instructing. The examination expects to pick up a top to bottom comprehension of the usage of video materials in the EFL classroom, and investigating the reason(s) for consolidating video materials into the EFL classroom from the points of view of educators and understudies. The examination draws on the worldview of interpretivism utilizing its epistemology and reasoning as a supporting position. For picking up thick data, the scientist utilized the technique for semi-organized meetings with the educator and understudy tests. Understandings of information demonstrated that instructors and understudies are exceptionally inspired by the usage of video materials in the EFL classroom because of specific reasons. Because of the discoveries of information examination, the investigation offers various ramifications and proposals that are of an incentive for educators who are engaged with the cycle of ELT.

Keywords: material design, material development, video materials, EFL classroom; showing systems; general media apparatuses.

Аннотация. Это исследование имеет тенденцию к использованию видеоматериалов в качестве фундаментальной техники при планировании затрат времени на материалы в области инструктажа EFL / ESL. Экзамен предполагает всестороннее понимание использования видеоматериалов в классе EFL и изучение причин объединения видеоматериалов в классе EFL с точки зрения преподавателей и студентов. Исследование опирается на мировоззрение интерпретивизма, используя его эпистемологию и

рассуждения в качестве вспомогательной позиции. Для сбора толстых данных ученый использовал технику полуорганизованных встреч с преподавателем и тестов дублера. Понимание информации показало, что преподаватели и дублеры также очень вдохновлены использованием видеоматериалов в классе EFL по определенным причинам. В свете открытий, сделанных в результате изучения информации, исследование предлагает различные ответвления и предложения, которые являются стимулом для преподавателей, участвующих в цикле ELT.

Ключевые слова: материальный дизайн, разработка материалов, видеоматериалы, класс EFL; показательные системы; средства массовой информации общего назначения.

INTRODUCTION

In the time of present-day English language showing when the emphasis has been on the open necessities and interests of the understudies, educators need to consider various advancements to bring to the classroom. As an outcome of the status of the English language as the global language, the accentuation has been on talking and tuning in as two basic abilities in imparting among individuals everywhere in the world. The consistently developing necessities of the tuning in and talking aptitudes have moved the accentuation from learning the punctuation and writing of the language to the open requirements and abilities. Accordingly, engaging the relational abilities requires dominating the talking and listening aptitudes which are considered as the establishment of the language that encourages the learning of different abilities. Presumably, that informative language instruction (CLT) is the best methodology in this regard. In like manner, keeping up the informative methodology in English language learning requires numerous issues to be considered by course architects and educators, for example, course plan, classroom philosophy, materials plan, evaluation, and so forth. Because of the intricacy and trouble of talking and listening in light of the partner aptitudes and components, it is

imperative to think about any rousing and powerful procedures that help uphold and animate understudies' learning. Among these successful procedures are recordings, movies, and TV shows. In contrast with the course books and other conventional materials that may neglect to adjust to understudies' necessities and interests, video materials have an incredible degree of premium as they bring genuineness, reality, adaptability, and assortment to the EFL classroom and educational program improvement. ^[1]

A few exact exploration contemplates have demonstrated the value and the effect of sight and sound on individuals in different fields, for example, strategy, wellbeing, economy, and training is no exemption. The writing on foreign language materials plan and a few experimental examinations accentuated the significance of using films in EFL education based on upgrading understudies' open abilities and fitness. Mixed media assumes an extraordinary function in the improvement of English language capability. Video materials have been broadly utilized in EFL classrooms as a result of their relationship with open language education notwithstanding their part in encouraging language learning and animating the understudies. Instructors and course fashioners should be more worried about incorporating video materials into classroom learning. Educationally, the objective behind this is to open understudies to the normal utilization of language. Fusing films into classroom instruction furnishes students with "multi-tactile information that is near genuine correspondence". It is additionally accepted that video materials permit both instructing and figuring out how to turn out to be more important and intriguing, and dynamic. Furthermore, recordings give different offices, for example, captions, play controls, and inscriptions. Likewise, their handiness lies in presenting understudies to local speakers through an assortment of recordings, for

¹ Amin, B. M., Benachaiba, C., & Guemide, B. (2012). Using Multimedia to motivate students in EFL classrooms: A case study of English master's students at Jijel University, Algeria. *Malaysian Journal of Distance Education*, 14(2), 63-81.

example, films, TV notices, communication, and so on. Significantly, video materials illuminate the hindrances of heading out to English local talking nations to meet local speakers.

In the period of innovation, educators and course planners can utilize computerized recordings as per understudies' requirements and interests, and with the sort of subject or course. For instance, the talking course should be upheld by video materials and exercises as per the prospectus and sort of subjects. In the setting where the current examination happens, educators are given as Toohey states the upside of planning the courses they instruct as this mirrors "their power over educational program". While trying to improve the talking and listening aptitudes a few educators chose to incorporate video materials into classroom instructing for showing an assortment of subjects. Albeit some of them are worried about showing subjects, for example, composing, perusing, Grammar, and tuning in, they use recordings alongside course readings, worksheets, and different materials. They accept that the talking ability is extremely testing as it happens in an EFL climate where there is an absence of introduction to the characteristic utilization of the language and restricted act of the English language. This makes it hard for understudies to impart in English properly and successfully. They additionally accept that offering one course for oral correspondence and talking abilities with three credits for every week isn't sufficient for dominating talking capability. In this regard, educators have a part in planning, contextualizing, and adjusting materials as per the requirements and interests of understudies. The principal motivation behind the investigation is to add to information about planning and utilizing video materials by instructors at the tertiary training level. For this, the examination intends to pick up a top to bottom comprehension of the use of video materials in the EFL classroom and investigating the reason(s) for fusing video materials into the EFL classroom from the points of view of educators and understudies. Thus, the examination draws on the accompanying exploration questions:

- Why are EFL educators worried about joining video materials into a wide range of language subjects?
- How do educators plan their video materials corresponding to all language courses?
- How do understudies in education system profit by joining video materials into the EFL classroom?

Looking at the writing audit and observational exploration concerning the academic utilization of video materials as an instructional apparatus, it has been seen that the fundamental spotlight has been on analyzing the impacts of video materials on specific aptitudes. To put it another way, the primary spotlight has been on the arrangement or looking at the function of video materials on a specific subject that may be talking, tuning in, understanding cognizance, composing, or syntax. In any case, this examination endeavors to comprehend and inspect coordinating video materials in a wide range of subjects including talking, tuning in, perusing, composing, and punctuation.^[2] As far as anyone is concerned, no investigation in the current writing has been led for this reason. Hence, this investigation endeavors to close this exploration hole.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous educators and specialists know about the upsides of video materials in language classrooms. Likewise, our understudies are knowledgeable about movies and TV and YouTube shows. In EFL, the emphasis on utilizing true materials, which video medium is important for, has been a partner with the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) that arose since the 1980s. As per the CLT approach, language instructors need to consider utilizing an assortment of utilizing real

² Asokhia, M. O. (2009). Improvisation/teaching aids: aid to effective teaching of English language. *International Journal of Education and Science*, 1(2), 79-85.

materials in the EFL classroom to support correspondence and association among understudies. Numerous researchers have stressed the significance of joining video materials into the EFL classroom as a wellspring of presentation to the foreign language. Sherman gives enticing contention respect to joining video material into the language classroom. For this reason, she gave exercises telling the best way to utilize video to bring genuine language and culture into the EFL/ESL classroom. An incredible bit of scope of bringing video materials into the classroom is presenting understudies to the way of life of the objective language. By watching motion pictures and recordings understudies can learn viewpoints, customs, and estimations of the English-talking nations. Also, utilizing motion pictures in the EFL classroom furnishes understudies with "multi-tangible info that is near genuine correspondence".

The premium in using the video as a mechanism of guidance has pulled in the consideration of numerous scientists to examine the advantages of utilizing recordings in the EFL/ESL classrooms. For instance, a few examinations have inspected the function of video materials in bringing genuineness, inspiration, and variety to the classroom that conventional course books cannot bring. A few examinations have conceded that giving legitimate materials can emphatically impact understudies' inspiration regarding picking up an uplifting mentality for learning the English language culture and taking an interest in serious gathering exercises. Amine, Benachaiba, and Guemide through their contextual analysis have discovered that "the accessibility of interactive media was a dynamic and testing persuading factor in EFL classroom". Also, Huang has upheld the utilization of video materials for animating understudies with low English capability. Mentally, and especially corresponding to understudy inspiration, there are powerful factors that assume an incredible function in understudies' learning. Recordings can be considered as one of these components that add to understudies' learning by raising their consideration and limiting their uneasiness while seeing recordings. In language learning, video materials comprise a sort of general media helps that help

understudies in learning a foreign language through hearing and review. Richards and Renedy call attention to that "video is a very thick medium, one which fuses a wide assortment of visual components and an incredible scope of sound involvement with expansion to communicated in language". In the time of innovation, video is considered as an instructive innovation apparatus that has been consolidated into the course prospectus plan for instructive circumstances and EFL/ESL classroom.

Video materials include various sorts. They can be introduced in the type of movies, TV promotions, news, and communicates, and expertly planned tapes. As of late, computerized recordings have gotten so famous that are valuable in making ordinary English available to all students everywhere in the world. Recordings can be expertly intended for classroom guidance. Video is viewed as a significant instrument in instructing a foreign language as they bring the normal utilization of the language by local speakers into the classroom. Through video materials, understudies can learn paralinguistic highlights, for example, motions, non-verbal communication, and various articulations. Also, recordings help change the daily practice of exercises, societies, and course readings that help understudies better comprehend through "visual and sound hints to signifying". Video materials should be separated from sound materials as the last alludes to the content that can be recorded in a tape or CD to tune in. Video materials, then again, allude to general media materials that can be heard and seen simultaneously, for example, motion pictures, recordings, news, and so forth. It is commonly perceived and acknowledged that the utilization of video materials in the EFL classroom is an extraordinary device for encouraging learning and rousing understudies who are experiencing an absence of training and introduction to local speakers. In this manner, it is significant for educators to utilize them as another option or help material in various zones of the English language. Utilizing recordings in the EFL classroom has a few preferences that are summed up in the areas beneath. ^[3]

³ Cepon, S. (2013). Effective Use of the Media: Video in the Foreign Language Classroom. *Medij.*

Legitimacy Video materials including film scenes, advertisements, melodies, give a degree of validness to understudies learning using establishing a common habitat inside the classroom. As such, recordings give a real contribution to students. This aide understudies not just comprehend the genuine utilization of the language, yet additionally to see parts of correspondence, for example, motions, non-verbal communication, and setting signs. These viewpoints can't be seen by methods for made materials or course readings that are just intended for instructive purposes. Besides, watching recordings helps students in obtaining the language which is simpler in learning a foreign language than strategies for perusing and understanding a language.

In language learning, genuineness alludes to "the language delivered by local speakers for local speakers in a specific language network". Credible materials are significant for supporting the open language instructing (CLT) that underlines the informative capacity of language more than its primary capacity. As indicated by techniques for language instructing should be more normal inside the classroom since language learning in a naturalistic climate is more fruitful and successful than learning in an unnatural climate. The open methodology underscores naturalism in foreign language learning. Video materials can be a valuable instrument to assist understudies with learning English as a foreign language as opposed to learning it intentionally. Along these lines, educators should utilize an assortment of chances to assist understudies with utilizing language for informative purposes.

CONCLUSION

The key subjects rising out of the information examination give certainly viable ramifications that can be useful for the establishment where this investigation happens and for instructors who are worried about planning and choosing their EFL materials. The outcomes infer that the educators in this tertiary setting show an

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incredible propensity towards the utilization of recordings in their classroom as an academic method for improving their understudies' tuning in and talking abilities. This infers that instructors of English can consolidate video materials for showing a wide range of subjects (Reading, Writing, Grammar, Speaking, Listening, and so on) Thusly, educators can exploit all subjects for the improvement and strengthening of talking and oral correspondence. A subsequent ramification dependent on educator and understudy interviews sees the intensity of recordings as a successful methodology that helps with animating understudies and urging them to engage in classroom conversation and exercises. The third ramifications identify with the conviction that instructors should have an imperative part in planning video materials and fusing them as per the sort of point and subject. Likewise, educators should know that there are sure issues that should be thought about while choosing video materials, for example, understudies' logical culture, language capability level, interest, and age. Because of what is accounted for above we comprehend that for these educators material advancement isn't just a matter of utilizing course books. Or maybe it involves settling on choices and alternatives to introduce materials that go in arrangement with objectives and targets and serve to fulfill understudies' requirements. This is viable with what Graves states that "... a significant part of materials improvement is settling on decisions... you need to settle on decisions dependent on what you need your understudies to pick up as indicated by your objectives and goals and your schedule center". In light of educator interviews, it has been demonstrated that the instructor members utilize the reading material endorsed by the office. Notwithstanding, they accept that the sole dependence on the reading material for conveying a course is deficient. Consequently, they chose to intervene between the course reading and other advantageous materials, for example, video materials and sites. They accept that such intervention of materials accomplishes a few purposes, for example, inspiration, variety, adaptability, and fulfilling understudies' necessities. The instructor members consider recordings as a viable apparatus that has a few preferences. Another significant highlight feature is

that there are a few factors that should be viewed when utilizing video materials. These variables include understudies' way of life, language capability level, interests, and needs. Additionally, instructors should consider whether the recordings help understudies arrive at their objectives and goals or not. At the end of the day, recordings should not be chosen to shading the exercise; rather they should be chosen based on the course learning goals.

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